

Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav Case (India v. Pakistan) and the Decision of International Court of Justice: An Analysis

Farzeen

Department of Political Science, University of Science and Technology Bannu, Pakistan

Hashmat Ullah Khan

Institute of Middle Eastern Studies, Northwest University, Xi'an, China

Aiman Niaz

School of English, Institute of Management Sciences, Pakistan

Shayan Ul Abidin

Department of Data Science, Institute of Management Sciences, Pakistan

Zafar Niaz

Assistant Director Coordination and Protocol, KPK Assembly, Pakistan

Amsh Bin Yasir

Department of Computer Science, National College of Business Administration & Economic, Pakistan

Abstract

The main objective of this study is to analyse the decision of the ICJ in Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav case in the light of public and private International Law. This case is related to the arrest of Indian spy Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav by Pakistan and his death sentence. He was engaged in espionage and terrorist activities in Pakistan which he himself confessed in his video statement after arrest. This article analyses that how international law and particularly the ICJ affects the life of a spy engaged in espionage and the right of states. The case is related to the interpretation of Article 36 of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations of 1963. Different from the previous cases of consular rights heard by ICJ, in this case India requested relief of the convicted that consist of the revocation of the Kulbhushan awarded by Pakistani court, release from detention, and handover to India. ICJ decided that Pakistan had violated the article 36 of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations by neglecting to inform Kulbhushan about his rights under this article, by neglecting to inform India immediately without delay about his arrest and by depriving India of the consular access to the detainee. ICJ added in its decision for the review of the case and reconsideration of sentence of Kulbhushan in Pakistan but did not provide for his release.

Keywords: *Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav, Vienna Convention on Consular Relations, International Court of Justice, India, Pakistan.*

Suggested citation: Farzeen, Khan, H.U., Niaz, A., Ul Abidin, S., Niaz, Z., & Yasir, A.B. (2024). Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav Case (India v. Pakistan) and the Decision of International Court of Justice: An Analysis. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 3-11. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(1).01

Introduction

Jadhav Case (India v. Pakistan) is about the arrest, detention and death sentence of Kulbhushan Jadhav by Pakistani authorities, who was convicted of involving in terrorism and spying in Pakistan (Kattan, 2020). He was born in Sangli city of the Indian state of Maharashtra on April 15, 1969, was arrested by

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Pakistan in its Balochistan province on March 3, 2016 (Wasilewski and Zenkiewicz, 2018) with a fake passport under the name of Hossein Mubarak Patel. Pakistan claimed that he is Indian spy involved in espionage and terrorism in the country. In favour of these claims, Pakistan released a video in which Kulbhushan confessed his involvement in supporting and helping terrorism and espionage in Pakistan at the behest of Research and Analysis Wing (RAW). He said, "I am still a serving officer in the Indian Navy and is due for retirement by 2022 as a commissioned officer" (Dawn, April 10, 2017). Further in he said that he had started the intelligence activities in 2003 and founded a business in the Chahbahar city of Iran, from where he was able to come to Pakistan without any detection. He had directed many rebellious movements and terrorist attacks in Balochistan province and in Karachi city of Sindh province, the commercial hub of Pakistan. According to him, his job was to do meetings with Baloch insurgent groups and help them to fight against Pakistani authorities and kill and kidnap citizens of Pakistan for their cause until arrested by the security authorities of Pakistan on March 3, 2016 (Dawn, April 10, 2017). In his video he clearly confessed and accepted that he did operations to destabilise Pakistan from the Chahbahar port of Iran and that RAW had been funding the sectarian violence in Balochistan. On the other hand, India said that he is an ex-Navy officer (Rajput, 2017) and now he was doing a legal business of operating ferry from the Iranian port town of Bandar Abbas. India further alleged that Jadhav was abducted by Pakistan from Iran (India Today, April 10, 2017).

The Jadhav case is fourth dispute come before the ICJ to interpret the article 36 of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations. Unlike the previous case of consular cases, India also requested relief that consist of the termination of his sentence in Pakistan, release from jail, and safe and sound move to India. Pakistan stopped the implementation of his sentence after filing an appeal against the decision of Pakistani court at the ICJ on May 18, 2017. ICJ announced its final decision on July 17, 2019, denied the Indian appeal for the release of Jadhav and told Pakistan to stop his execution. The court decided that Pakistan will have to review the whole procedure of the prosecution and verdict of Jadhav and give consular access to India.

Literature Review

The Kulbhushan case between India and Pakistan is the fourth of its kind before the ICJ. Before this the Avena case and LaGrand case were also filed in ICJ to determine consular relations under Vienna Convention. Despite its importance, very few studies have been done in this study area. The literature now available has examined primarily consular relations under the Vienna Convention and the respective responsibilities of states. Except for a few studies (Kattan, (2020), Turkey (2019), and Wasilewski and Zenkiewicz (2018)) there is lack of literature that debates Kulbhushan case. This piece of study is an effort to fill the gap.

On 2 March 1999, the Federal Republic of Germany submitted an application to the Court's Registry, initiating proceedings against the United States of America on purported breaches of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations dated 24 April 1963. Germany asserted that, in 1982, the authorities of Arizona detained two German nationals, Karl and Walter LaGrand, who were tried and sentenced to death without being informed of their rights, as mandated by Article 36, paragraph 1 (b), of the Vienna Convention (Jennings, 2002). The International Court of Justice determined that it has jurisdiction over all of Germany's arguments, which were deemed admissible. The Court noted a violation of Article 36, paragraph 1 (b), of the Vienna Convention (Frowein, 2002). The Court emphasized that the United States of America violated its obligation under the Order indicating provisional measures by not taking all necessary actions to prevent the execution of Walter LaGrand while awaiting the final decision of the International Court of Justice in the case (Weisburd, 2000). In the LaGrand case, the ICJ asserted that the United States must provide the review and reconsideration of the conviction and punishment, considering the infringement of rights stipulated in the VCCR. Likewise, case concerning Avena and Other Mexican Nationals (Mexico v. United States of America), on 9 January 2003, Mexico initiated legal proceedings against the United States regarding purported infringements of Articles 5 and 36 of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations of 24 April 1963, pertaining to 54 Mexican nationals sentenced

to death in various U.S. states. Simultaneously with its Application, Mexico submitted a request for the indication of provisional measures, seeking, among other things, that the United States undertake all necessary actions to prevent the execution of any Mexican national and to refrain from any actions that could compromise the rights of Mexico or its nationals concerning any decision the Court may render on the merits of the case. Following the public hearings regarding provisional measures on 21 January 2003, the Court issued an Order on 5 February 2003, mandating that the "United States of America must take all necessary measures to ensure that the individuals involved are not executed pending the final judgment in these proceedings" (Steinmark, 2004). Another case of such kind appeared filled in ICJ was between Paraguay v. US. On 3 April 1998, the Republic of Paraguay submitted an Application to the Registry, initiating proceedings against the United States of America on purported breaches of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations of 24 April 1963. Paraguay established the Court's jurisdiction pursuant to Article 36, paragraph 1, of the Statute and Article I of the Optional Protocol accompanying the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations, which confers jurisdiction to the Court for resolving disputes related to the interpretation or application of that Convention. In its Application, Paraguay stated that, in 1992, authorities in the Commonwealth of Virginia arrested a Paraguayan national, charged him with culpable homicide, convicted him, and sentenced him to death without informing him of his rights as mandated by Article 36, paragraph 1 (b), of the Convention. The rights included the entitlement to seek notification of his arrest and imprisonment to the relevant consular office of his country and the right to correspond with that office. The Applicant additionally argued that the authorities of the Commonwealth of Virginia had not informed the Paraguayan consulate personnel, who were thus only able to provide help from 1996, when the Paraguayan Government became aware of the situation via its own efforts. Paraguay requested the Court to determine and declare that the United States of America had breached its international legal duties to Paraguay and that Paraguay was entitled to "restitution in kind." On 3 April 1998, Paraguay made a Request for the indication of interim measures to prevent the execution of the individual implicated while awaiting the Court's determination. On 9 April 1998, after a public hearing, the Court issued an Order on Paraguay's Request for the indication of temporary measures. The Court unanimously determined that the United States of America must use all available means to prevent the execution of the concerned Paraguayan citizen while awaiting the Court's verdict. By letter dated 2 November 1998, Paraguay expressed its desire to terminate the proceedings with prejudice. The United States of America agreed to the cessation on 3 November. On 10 November 1998, the Court issued an Order documenting the discontinuation and ordering the removal of the case from the List.

Decision of Pakistani Court

After the arrest he was trailed through "Field General Court" under the Pakistan Army Act which found him guilty and awarded him death sentence. The trial of Jadhav began on September 21, 2016, under a Field General Court Martial. On January 23, 2017, Pakistan's Ministry of Foreign Affairs sent a letter to the High Commission of India in Islamabad requesting assistance in procuring evidence for the criminal inquiry. India sought consular access to Jadhav; however, Pakistan's Foreign Ministry said that India's request will be evaluated based on its answer to Pakistan's appeal for cooperation in the investigative process and the prompt administration of justice. On March 31, 2017, India said that consular access to Jadhav was a crucial requirement for verifying the facts and comprehending the circumstances of his stay in Pakistan. However, less than two weeks later, on April 10, 2017, Pakistan said that Jadhav had received a death sentence. Since Jadhav's apprehension, India has been denied consular access, although he was assigned a defense officer in accordance with legal rules throughout his Field General Court Martial trial. He received a death sentence from the FGCM on April 10, 2017 (Dawn, April 10, 2017).

Decision of International Court of Justice

On 8 May 2017, India initiated proceedings against Pakistan regarding alleged violations of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations of 24 April 1963, specifically concerning the detention and trial of Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav. Article 36 of this convention stipulates that foreign nationals who are arrested or detained must be notified "without delay" of their right to have their embassy or consulate informed of the arrest, and consular officers are entitled to visit nationals of the sending State who are imprisoned, in custody, or detained, to communicate with them and arrange for their legal representation (Baily, 2001). The mother of Mr. Jadhav insisted to file an appeal from that sentence within the Pakistani legal system, India decided to file case in International Court of Justice. India said that Pakistan did not promptly notify it of the arrest and custody of its citizen. It additionally asserted that Mr. Jadhav was not apprised of his rights under Article 36 of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations, and that India's consular officials were denied access to Mr. Jadhav during his custody, detention, and imprisonment, preventing them from communicating or corresponding with him or facilitating his legal representation. India cited Article 36 of the Court's Statute and Article I of the Optional Protocol to the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations on the Compulsory Settlement of Disputes as the foundation for the Court's jurisdiction in its Application. On the same day, India submitted a Request for the indication of provisional measures, urging the Court to instruct Pakistan to implement all necessary measures to prevent the execution of Mr. Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav and to ensure that no actions are undertaken that could compromise the rights of the Republic of India or Mr. Kulbhushan Sudhir Jadhav regarding any decision the Court may render on the merits of the case. India accused Pakistan of: violation of the rights of Mr Jadhav to be informed of his rights to seek assistance from India (article 36(1)(b) of VCCR); violation of article 14 of the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, because Pakistan fail to accord Mr Jadhav 'elementary rights of the accused'; and violation of article 36(1)(a) and article 36(1)(c) of VCCR by denying India of the exercise of its right to seek consular access to Mr Jadhav, to arrange for his legal representation and to correspond and converse with him. By using Article 36(1), instead of Article 36(2), of the ICJ Statute, India has limited the final scope of its application to remedies for lack of access to Mr. Jadhav. On the other hand, by using article 36(1) of the Statute India escapes from the dispute and possible objections to compulsory jurisdiction in light of the Pakistan and India reservations to the ICJ jurisdiction (Wasilewski and Żenkiewicz, 2018).

Initially, Pakistan asserted that the ICJ lacked jurisdiction over the issue but was unsuccessful in contesting jurisdiction and admission. Pakistan contended that its statement under Article 36(2) of the Statute, in conjunction with the 2008 Bilateral Agreement, renders the VCCR inapplicable to the present case. Furthermore, Pakistan contends that the VCCR is inapplicable to those accused of espionage and terrorism operations. Consequently, based on those considerations, the ICJ lacks jurisdiction to adjudicate this issue. Furthermore, it said that India's plea could neither be allowed nor considered, since it had not approached the ICJ with "clean hands" (Dumberry and Aubin, 2013). This legal concept indicated that India's own misconduct in failing to provide enough help in the inquiry precluded it from seeking a judicial redress. Pakistan contested the relevance of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations in this instance by asserting, firstly, that it is inapplicable to alleged espionage and terrorism cases, and secondly, that a 2008 bilateral agreement between the two nations altered the application of the Vienna Convention to sensitive political and security matters (Pakistan India Agreement N0. 54471). The Court in its Order of 18 May, 2017, after hearing held on 15 May 2017 decided that: it has prima facie jurisdiction under Article 1 of the Optional Protocol of the VCCR to adjudicate the dispute between the Parties. The ICJ completely dismissed both challenges. The case was deemed admissible, and the ICJ affirmed its jurisdiction based on the Optional Protocol to the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations (United Nations, 1961), to which both governments are parties. The ICJ dismissed these claims, since the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations does not provide for any exceptions or modifications. It also underscored that acknowledging espionage or terrorism as exceptions would enable nations to evade their responsibilities under the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations in contentious situations.

On 18 May 2017, the Court issued an Order instructing Pakistan to use all available means to prevent the execution of Mr. Jadhav until a final resolution of the matter, and to report to the Court on all actions

taken to implement that Order. The ICJ has issued a binding order to Pakistan, instructing it to implement all necessary steps to postpone the execution of Jadhav until the court renders its final ruling (Jadhav, 2019). Then the execution of Kulbhushan was stayed by Pakistan. It is worth mentioning, that under article 41 of the Statute “the Court shall have the power to indicate, if it considers that circumstances so require, any provisional measures which ought to be taken to preserve the respective rights of either party”.

The hearings for the case began in February 2019, during which the Court first delineated the context of the dispute before determining its authority to consider India's allegations about purported infringements of the Vienna Convention. The Court thereafter examined the three challenges to inclusion presented by Pakistan, which were to India's purported abuse of process, abuse of rights, and illegal behavior. The Court determined that India's Application was permissible. The Court systematically evaluated each of Pakistan's three arguments on the validity of the Vienna Convention. The Court determined that none of Pakistan's arguments were valid and ruled that the Vienna Convention applied to the case, "irrespective of the claims that Mr. Jadhav was involved in espionage." The ICJ observed that its jurisdiction in the case arose from Article 1 of the Optional Protocol and that Pakistan had not contested that the dispute related to the interpretation or application of the VCCR. Next, the Court examined India's claim that Pakistan had acted in violation of its obligations under Article 36 of the Vienna Convention, by failing to inform India, without delay, of Mr. Jadhav's detention. The Court observed that Pakistan did not contest India's assertion that Mr. Jadhav had not been informed of his rights under Article 36, of the Convention, and thus concluded that Pakistan had breached its obligation under that provision. After unanimously finding it had jurisdiction, fifteen judges of the ICJ, with only Judge ad hoc Jilani dissenting, held on the merits that Pakistan had breached VCCR Article 36 by failing to inform Jadhav without delay of his rights under that provision; by failing to notify without delay the appropriate consular post of India in Pakistan of his detention; and by depriving India of its right to communicate with Jadhav, to visit him in detention, and arrange for his legal representation. In addition, the Court, with only Judge ad hoc Jilani dissenting, found that Pakistan is under an obligation to inform Jadhav of his rights without further delay and is obliged to provide Indian consular officers access to him. The broader importance of the Jadhav Case is that it makes it clear that these obligations apply to all VCCR party nationals in the territory of another state party, including those accused of terrorism and espionage, even where their nationality is disputed by one of the parties. In his dissenting opinion, judge ad hoc Jilani drew attention to the evidence presented by Pakistan as to the authenticity of Jadhav's passport, referencing the expert's report, which had concluded that the Indian passport was genuine, and detailing some of the offenses Jadhav was accused of committing in Pakistan. In Jilani's view, the issuance of a valid Indian passport with a false Muslim identity for the express purpose of engaging in terrorist activities for the Baloch Liberation Movement was a “abuse of process”. Next, Jilani reasoned that the 2008 Agreement was meant to clarify and inform certain provisions of the VCCR given the special circumstances faced by the two countries He also expressed his view that the delay in notifying the Indian consular authorities about the arrest of Jadhav was understandable, especially after he disclosed that he was involved in espionage and terrorism in two cities of Pakistan. Given the magnitude of the charges committed by Jadhav, the damage they had presented to the Pakistan's national security, and that other accomplices whom he mentioned were still being probed, a delay “of three weeks between his arrest and notification [was] reasonable and thus did not amount to a breach of Article 36 (1)(b) of the Vienna Convention”.

The Court addressed Pakistan's purported failure to promptly notify India of Mr. Jadhav's arrest and detention, as stipulated in Article 36, paragraph 1 (b), of the Vienna Convention. It concluded that Pakistan's neglect to inform Mr. Jadhav of his rights necessitated its obligation to notify India's consular post of his arrest and detention. This obligation is further supported by the rights of consular officers, as outlined in Article 36, paragraph 1 (c), which include visiting the national, communicating with him, and facilitating his legal representation. The Court observed that Pakistan informed India of Mr. Jadhav's arrest and detention on 25 March 2016, approximately three weeks after the arrest. Given the specific circumstances, the Court ruled that Pakistan breached its duty to notify the consular post "without delay," as required by Article 36 of the Vienna Convention.

The Court next addressed India's third assertion about Pakistan's purported obstruction of Indian consular officials from communicating with Mr. Jadhav, noting in this context that "Article 36, paragraph 1, creates individual rights, which, by virtue of Article I of the Optional Protocol, may be invoked in this Court by the national State of the detained person". The Court determined that Pakistan's refusal to grant Indian consular officers access to Mr. Jadhav was unjustifiable, as India's purported lack of cooperation in the investigation did not absolve Pakistan of its duty to provide consular access. Moreover, Mr. Jadhav's decision to be represented by a legally competent defense officer did not negate the consular officials' entitlement to facilitate his legal counsel. The Court concluded that Pakistan violated its obligations under Article 36, paragraph 1 (a) and (c), of the Vienna Convention by denying India's consular officers access to Mr. Jadhav, infringing upon their rights to visit, communicate, and arrange legal representation for him. Concerning India's petition for the Court to nullify the military court's ruling and prevent Pakistan from enforcing the sentence or conviction, as well as its additional plea for the Court to instruct Pakistan to annul the military court's decision, release Mr. Jadhav, and ensure his safe return to India, the Court determined that India's arguments were untenable. The Court determined that Pakistan was obligated to offer, through its preferred methods, an effective review and reconsideration of Mr. Jadhav's conviction and sentence, ensuring that the impact of the violation of rights outlined in Article 36 of the Vienna Convention was fully acknowledged.

The ICJ issued its final ruling in the matter on July 17, 2019, denying India's petition for Jadhav's release and instructing Pakistan to halt the execution. The ICJ mandated that Pakistan to reassess the whole trial and conviction process of Jadhav and provide India consular access. Subsequent to the directive, Islamabad provided consular access to Jadhav. On September 2, 2019, Indian Chargé d'Affaires Gaurav Ahluwalia conferred with Jadhav in a Pakistani sub-jail. Following the ICJ's ruling, Pakistan opted to endorse the bill for the reassessment of Kulbhushan Jadhav's conviction to prevent contravening the ICJ's judgment. There might be several implications if Pakistan fails to comply with the International Court of Justice's judgment. The realization of such fact has instilled optimism in Indian authorities. Subsequently, Pakistan, with the endorsement of the National Assembly's Law and Justice Committee, has presented a bill to review Jadhav's conviction, in accordance with the guidelines of the International Court of Justice (Review and Reconsideration) Ordinance. The legislation permits Jadhav to submit an appeal over his conviction to a high court. India demands the appointment of an Indian lawyer or a Queen's Counsel for death-row inmate Kulbhushan Jadhav to provide a fair and impartial trial in this nation. Pakistan rejected India's request. Pakistan permits only licensed attorneys to represent clients in its courts. Pakistan stated that it is not legally feasible to permit an Indian lawyer to represent Indian death row inmate Kulbhushan Jadhav in a court within its jurisdiction. This aligns with international legal standards (Moses, 1995). The ICJ ruling explicitly states that the review and reconsideration process will occur in Pakistani courts in accordance with Pakistani law.

India celebrated the final decision as its "overwhelming win", but it is not at all. The ruling was not entirely unfavorable for Pakistan, since India failed to get the extensive relief it desired. The ICJ denied India's petition to assert that the judgment rendered by Pakistan's military tribunal contravened the VCCR and international law, and to mandate Pakistan to release Jadhav and ensure his safe repatriation to India. The ICJ did not invalidate the death sentence imposed by Pakistan's military tribunal, nor did it mandate the release of Jadhav to India. Nonetheless, the ruling was not entirely unfavorable for Pakistan. India notably failed to get the ambitious relief it sought.

Considering the remedy provided by the court, it is pertinent to analyze the implementation results of analogous instances prior to the ICJ. The conclusions and solutions in the Jadhav case concerning Article 36 of the VCCR parallel those in the LaGrand case (Germany v. United States) and the Avena case (Mexico v. United States). The ICJ determined in both rulings that the US violated its commitments under Article 36 of the VCCR and mandated it to provide "effective review and reconsideration" of the sentences and convictions of foreign citizens (Tirkey, 2019). Numerous US rulings have asserted that Article 36 rights are unenforceable in domestic courts and that no remedy under domestic law may be granted, even in cases of established violations. Numerous domestic courts conducted a "review and reconsideration" without acknowledging or contemplating the conclusions of the LaGrand and Avena

cases. Furthermore, domestic courts determined that a breach of Article 36 does not nullify any prior procedural precedents. The accused foreign national cannot dismiss any declarations or admissions made during the violation of Article 36. If this is the case, Jadhav's many filmed admissions, the authenticity of which has been vehemently disputed by India, would persist as incriminating evidence in Pakistan's courts. Consequently, it remains to be determined the degree to which Pakistan's courts would conduct a thorough review and reassessment of the ruling. Aside from the mandate for Pakistan to provide a fair trial, India has little influence over the judicial process it opts to implement. The extent of Pakistan's adherence to the norms, principles, and judgments established by public international law is crucial. This concept provides no comfort to India. At this juncture, upon receiving consular access, India may endeavor to provide Jadhav with the most effective legal representation permissible under Pakistani law. In addition to this, India has other alternatives for redress if Pakistan's efforts are inadequate. Although ICJ rulings are conclusive and unappealable, India may seek to engage the court once again to:

- Interpret the ruling, should India and Pakistan disagree on its interpretation and extent, and
- To revise it, if new and crucial facts are discovered by India.

Although they are not appeals, they provide India an additional means of obtaining relief on certain eligible reasons. If Pakistan refuses to implement any of the ICJ's directives, India may seek recourse from the United Nations Security Council, which has the authority to enforce binding actions to actualize an ICJ ruling. This course of action relies on the consensus of the P5 for decision-making, which included Pakistan's steadfast ally, China. India might independently cut diplomatic relations, impose penalties, and advocate for public condemnation of Pakistan's conduct on the world arena.

Moreover, the Indian application has many long-standing repercussions on Pakistan-India bilateral relations. Apart from the outcome for the Jadhav case, the current proceedings can have far reaching repercussions for India-Pakistan relations. So far, the position of India was that all issues with Pakistan would be resolved rather bilaterally. As India's Congress spokesperson - Ajoy Kumar explained that "the best resolution is bilateral at all times, no matter how recalcitrant Pakistan is (The Times of India, May 11, 2017). Such an attitude can be explained by the threat that the conflicts, such as Kashmir issue or the Kishan Ganga power project, which were successfully kept at bay by India from the international courts, may finally be brought by Pakistan for an international adjudication. Therefore, some of the commentators from India (Sharma, 2017) see it as a possible definitive break from the attitude of India in the past to resolve all the issues with Pakistan on the bilateral plane (Trivedi, 2017). However, such an attitude may be assessed from the viewpoint of India, positively or negatively, for international law it is very good news. It means that finally some very tense and problematic issues between those two nations may be resolved on the international plane in a pacific manner. Frequently, the disputes presented to the ICJ pertain to significant matters for a State and its policies. The choices influence territorial conflicts, treaty interpretations, or international policy. This instance is analogous. It addresses the critical matter of consular rights. Moreover, as noted in the article, the current case may significantly facilitate international adjudication to settle any conflicts between the regional adversaries, India and Pakistan.

Conclusion

It is interesting to see how international law and the ICJ in particular can affect not only very important global issues and the rights of States, but also the life of an individual. The Jadhav Case clarifies that the obligations established by VCCR Article 36 are applicable to all nationals of VCCR state parties present in the territory of another state party, without exception, including individuals accused of terrorism and espionage, regardless of any disputes regarding their nationality by one of the parties. The near-unanimity of the ICJ in this judgment reinforces the Court's prior jurisprudence on Article 36 of the VCCR in the LaGrand and Avena and Other Mexican Nationals instances, particularly concerning the suitable remedies. The Jadhav Case aligns with the International Court of Justice's prior rulings on Article 36 of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations in LaGrand and Avena and Other Mexican Nationals, wherein the Court determined that Article 36 mandates the parties to ensure prompt consular

communication, access, and visitation for detained nationals of VCCR state parties. The Jadhav Case underscores that the responsibilities of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations (VCCR) extend to all citizens of member states inside the territory of another state party, including those accused of terrorism and espionage, regardless of any disputes over their nationality by one of the parties involved. The Jadhav Case clarifies that the obligations established by VCCR Article 36 are applicable to all nationals of VCCR state parties present in the territory of another state party, without exception, including individuals accused of terrorism and espionage, regardless of any disputes regarding their nationality by one of the parties.

On September 2, 2019, six weeks after the ICJ issued its ruling, Pakistan let Indian consular officials to see Jadhav for two hours, in accordance with the ICJ's order, notwithstanding his continued incarceration on death row for espionage, terrorism, and sabotage. In the absence of a diplomatic resolution, he must await the results of the review and reconsideration process in Pakistan.

Another aspect of the decision of this case is It is interesting to see how international law and the ICJ in particular can affect not only very important global issues and the rights of States, but also the life (and this time in a very ordinary meaning) of an individual. When skeptics assert that international law is ineffective, the case of Mr. Jadhav serves as a pertinent example, as international law has thus far deferred his execution and may potentially result in the reopening of his case and a retrial, this time with adequate consular assistance.

Acknowledgement

This study has been supported by the Chinese National Foreign Expert Project (No. Y20240154).

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Baily, B. M. (2001). People v. Madej: Illinois' violation of the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations. *Loyola University Chicago Law Journal*, 32(2), 471–510.
- Dawn. (2017, April 10). Who is Kulbhushan Jadhav? Retrieved from <https://www.dawn.com/news/1326117>
- Dumberry, P., & Aubin, G. D. (2013). The doctrine of “clean hands” and the inadmissibility of claims by investors breaching international human rights law. *Transnational Dispute Management*, 10(1), 1–10.
- Frowein, J. A. (2002). Provisional measures by ICJ, LaGrand case. *Heidelberg Journal of International Law*, 62(1), 55–60.
- India Today. (2017, April 10). Who is Kulbhushan Jadhav, the Indian sentenced to death in Pakistan? Retrieved from <https://www.indiatoday.in/fyi/story/kulbhushan-jadhav-indian-sentenced-to-death-pakistan-raw-970581-2017-04-10>
- International Court of Justice (ICJ). (2019, May 10). Decisions of Jadhav (India v. Pakistan) case. Retrieved from <https://www.icj-cij.org/en/case/168>
- Jennings, R. (2002). The LaGrand case. *Law and Practice of the International Court and Tribunals*, 1(1), 13–54.
- Kattan, V. (2020). Jadhav case (India v. Pakistan). *American Journal of International Law*, 114(2), 281–287. <https://doi.org/10.1017/ajil.2020.9>

The Times of India. (2017, May 11). Kulbhushan Jadhav case: Congress criticises, Left welcomes Hague move. Retrieved from <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/kulbhushanjadhav-case-congress-criticises-left-welcomes-hague-move/articleshow/58618278.cms>

Moses, F. (1995). International legal practice. *Fordham Law Review*, 4(2), 244–271.

Pakistan-India Agreement No. 54471. (2008, May 21). Agreement on consular access between the Government of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan and the Government of the Republic of India. Retrieved from <https://treaties.un.org/doc/Publication/UNTS/No%20Volume/54471/Part/I-54471-08000002804b7dde.pdf>

Rajput, R. (2017, April 12). Balochistan arrest: Kulbhushan Jadhav's father, uncle worked with Mumbai police. *The Indian Express*.

Steinmark, M. R. (2004). The case concerning Avena and other Mexican nationals (Mexico v. United States): A Mexican perspective on the fight for consular rights. *Law and Business Review of the Americas*, 10(2), 417–424.

Tirkey, A. (2019). The Kulbhushan Jadhav verdict: A certain win, with uncertain outcomes. New Delhi, India: Observer Research Foundation.

Trivedi, A. (2017, July 19). ICJ jurisdiction on bilateral issues: Possibilities regarding Jammu and Kashmir dispute. *JURIST*. Retrieved from <http://jurist.org/datetime/2017/02/abhishek-trivedi-icj-pandora.php>

United Nations. (1961, April 18). Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations. Vienna: United Nations Conference on Diplomatic Intercourse and Immunities. Retrieved from <https://2009-2017.state.gov/documents/organization/17843.pdf>

Wasilewski, T., & Żenkiewicz, M. (2018). The Jadhav case, India v. Pakistan (ongoing case at the International Court of Justice, 2017). *Comparative Law Review*, 23, 283–293. <https://doi.org/10.12775/CLR.2018.011>

Weisburd, A. M. (2000). International courts and American courts. *Michigan Journal of International Law*, 21(4), 877–939.

